

Supplementary:

Table S1 - Summary of Data by Urban versus Rural Classification for All Metals

Contaminant	Urban/Rural	Total Observations	% Exceedances
As	Urban	3181	54.39
	Rural	3765	66.96
	Mixed	1997	64.89
Pb	Urban	1585	25.62
	Rural	316	4.43
	Mixed	180	0
Mn	Urban	1577	13.95
	Rural	204	1.47
	Mixed	195	28.72
Cd	Urban	1029	26.34
	Rural	269	0
	Mixed	199	0
Sb	Urban	442	0
	Rural	28	35.71
	Mixed	0	-
Cr	Urban	1044	22.32
	Rural	217	0

	Mixed	134	14.18
Cu	Urban	1287	0.16
	Rural	229	0
	Mixed	301	5.32
Fe	Urban	1984	12.65
	Rural	254	1.57
	Mixed	288	7.64
Hg	Urban	435	4.78
	Rural	192	14.58
	Mixed	0	-
Ni	Urban	893	2.91
	Rural	135	0
	Mixed	152	12.5
Se	Urban	514	1.17
	Rural	139	82.73
	Mixed	0	-
U	Urban	291	3.78
	Rural	154	0
	Mixed	564	0

Table S2 - Summary of Data by JMP Improved versus Unimproved Classification for All Metals

Contaminant	Improved/Unimproved	Total Observations	% Exceedances
As	Improved	5295	61.25
	Unimproved	3648	63.16
Pb	Improved	1004	13.35
	Unimproved	1077	26.56
Mn	Improved	1009	9.42
	Unimproved	967	19.03
Cd	Improved	605	19.83
	Unimproved	892	16.93
Sb	Improved	272	0
	Unimproved	198	5.05
Cr	Improved	667	1.80
	Unimproved	728	32.97
Cu	Improved	752	0
	Unimproved	1065	1.69
Fe	Improved	1007	4.57
	Unimproved	1519	15.21
Hg	Improved	179	11.62

	Unimproved	448	6.25
Ni	Improved	587	0.34
	Unimproved	593	7.25
Se	Improved	351	1.71
	Unimproved	302	38.08
U	Improved	304	3.62
	Unimproved	705	0